

Flow-injection Spectrophotometric Determination of Nitrite in Water Samples

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A sensitive and rapid method is described for the determination of nitrite. Nitrite is reacted with 4-aminosalicylic acid in acidic medium to give diazonium ions and merged with a coupling agent (1-naphthol) in alkaline medium resulting in the formation of azo compound quantified spectrophotometrically at 515 nm. This method allows the determination of nitrite concentration in the range of $0.05 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ with a sampling rate of 180 h^{-1} at a relative standard deviation of $\leq 1\%$.

Nitrite is usually monitored regularly in water supplies as it is deemed to be potentially hazardous to health if their maximum admissible concentration (MAC) of 0.1 ppm is exceeded. Nitrites are an intermediate product, both in the oxidation of ammonia to nitrate and in the reduction of nitrate which occurs in waste water-treatment plants, water distribution systems and natural waters¹.

Numerous methods have been proposed for the determination of nitrite including amperometric², fluorometric³, spectrophotometric⁴ and voltametric⁵. In some of these reported methods several anions and cations interfere. The present investigation of nitrite determination in water samples is based on the formation of an azo dye with 1-naphthol in alkaline medium.

Results and Discussion

FIA configurations were optimised in order to obtain the best response in terms of sensitivity, sampling rate and reagent consumption using 5.0 ppm nitrite standard solution. The effect of $5-12.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ 4-aminosalicylic acid on the response of azo dye formation was examined. The results (Fig. 1) gave the most suitable response at 0.01 M 4-aminosalicylic acid prepared in 0.4 M hydrochloric acid.

The effect of coupling agent 1-naphthol concentration was tested on the colour intensity in the range 0.005–0.025 M. As shown in Fig. 1, significant result was obtained at the concentration level of 0.025 M 1-naphthol. Lower concentrations caused decrease in response due to multiple coupling⁶. During the optimisation of coupling agent concentration above 0.025 M, precipitates were observed in the mixing coil which caused non-steady baseline and therefore due to this effect 0.025 M 1-naphthol solution prepared in 0.3 M sodium hydroxide was selected for further studies.

Fig. 1. Effect of (■) 4-aminosalicylic acid and (●) 1-naphthol concentrations on the diazotisation process.

The effect of flow rates and mixing coil length was also calibrated to obtain the best overall response of the system in terms of sampling rate and sensitivity. A suitable response was achieved at a flow rate of 0.9 ml min^{-1} per channel and on further increase, the absorbance decreased due to low diazotisation process. Mixing coil length of 20 cm was used at which highest signals were obtained, above this length the signals decreased slightly.

Under the conditions established, the calibration graph was linear over the range 0.1–10 ppm nitrite with a regression coefficient for 6 concentrations of 0.995. The detection limit was $(2 \times \text{blank noise}) 0.05 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and the sampling throughput was 180 h^{-1} . The relative standard deviation for 12 measurements of 5.0 ppm nitrite was $\leq 1\%$.

In order to assess the possible analytical applications of this chromogenic reaction, the effect of diverse ions was studied by adding 5 ml of the

interferent solution (1000 ppm) to 10 ml of $5 \times 10^{-5} M$ nitrite and completing the volume to 50 ml. The following species had no effect on the peak absorbance of nitrite : sodium acetate, sodium carbonate, sodium chloride, sodium fluoride, potassium nitrate, sodium oxalate, sodium dihydrogen phosphate, sodium sulphate and sodium sulphite. However thiosulphate was effected on the peak absorbance which is rarely present in water samples.

The proposed analytical method was applied to four tap water samples collected in polyethylene vessels from various locations in the Quetta District. On the same day, each sample was filtered through a membrane filter ($0.45 \mu\text{m}$) and were examined immediately. The values obtained were 0.15, 0.20, 0.12 and 0.10 ppm as nitrite (average of six readings). The same tap water samples were analysed by the method of Zhou and Xie⁷ as a reference. The values obtained were 0.13, 0.15, 0.09 and 0.07 ppm as nitrite respectively.

The proposed method is simple, sensitive and comparatively selective. The results obtained are comparable with those achieved by other reported methods. The marked interference is from thiosulphate. This anion is rarely present in drinking water samples. However pretreatment of samples with an ion-exchange column would be a suitable remedy.

Experimental

All reagents were of AnalaR grade and distilled/deionised water was used. 4-Aminosalicylic acid solution ($0.01 M$) was prepared by dissolving sodium salt of 4-aminosalicylic acid dihydrate in $0.4 M$ HCl. 1-Naphthol solution ($0.025 M$) was prepared in $0.3 M$ NaOH. Nitrite stock solution was prepared by dissolving oven-dried sodium nitrite (0.15 g) in water (100 ml) and was treated with a few drops

of chloroform and kept in a refrigerator. From this stock dilute solutions were prepared by appropriate dilution with water.

The flow injection manifold used is schematically shown in Fig. 2. A peristaltic pump (Ismatec Reglo 100) was used for propelling the carrier and reagents. Nitrite standards ($25 \mu\text{l}$) were injected via a rotary valve (Rheodyne 5020). The maximum absorbance was monitored at 515 nm by flow

Fig 2. FIA Manifold for the determination of nitrite : R_1 =4-aminosalicylic acid solution, R_2 =1-naphthol solution, S=sample ($25 \mu\text{l}$) and W=waste.

through ($30 \mu\text{l}$) a LKB Novaspec 11 spectrophotometer.

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